

Findings: Human Resource Problem and Action Plan

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Human Resource Problem and Action Plan

Introduction

In The HR departments in many organizations have become strategic meaning that they are an integral part of the realization of the visions and missions of the organization. Various HR practices like Recruitment and selection induction and training, career development, succession planning, compensation management, outplacement and retirement are not being done in the conventional arbitrary method but they have to be in line with the strategic direction of the firm (Bloom, 2011).

This is why strategic decision making must precede the HR functions of the organizations because it is the strategic decisions made that will determine how the strategic functions will be carried out. An organization must therefore identify its missions and visions which must be articulated to all the shareholders. Clear visions and missions are very fundamental for the development of HR strategies because they have to be relevant with the literacy levels and the competencies of the employees who will have to face the challenge of delivering it (Budhwar, 2013).

Problem Statement

Human Resource professionals are closely involved in all aspects of employee turnover and occupy a unique role in the organization, interacting between executives and all other employees (Gentry, 2006). The Choiteram supermarket is facing problem of high employee turnover which is a challenge for its Human resource department. This is a major problem as

High employee turnover increases costs for the organization which in turn lowers the profitability (Guest, 2011).

Human Resource professionals are involved in organizational decision-making, liaising with senior leadership and with employees at all levels of the organization as an aspect of personnel administration and recruitment, selection, and termination (Gentry, 2006). This unique position gives Human Resources a clear overview of the personnel within the organization (Mathis, 2011).

Why is it a problem?

Employee turnover rates affect organizational profitability, due to the related high recruitment and training costs (Mello, 2014). Employees' commitment is based upon the five fundamental constructs of affective commitment, continuance commitment, Protestant Work Ethic, career commitment, and job involvement (Price, 2011). Affective commitment refers to an emotional attachment in which an employee feels he or she is part of an organization with similar goals).

The literature review will also cover human resources, reviewing and confirming the use of the human resource professionals as the source for the sample for the study. This will be due to their position within the organization, interacting at both leadership and employee levels (Tooksoon, 2011). Human Resource professionals are involved with the leadership team and the aspects of personnel administration and recruitment, selection, and termination .ensuring direct contact with personnel at all levels. This gives Human Resources an insight into leaders an insight into leaders and followers interactions within the organization (Wright, 2011).

Employee turnover rates have an effect on organizational profitability, due to the related high recruitment and training costs. This problem is not specific to the United States but is experienced worldwide. With globalization causing mergers and acquisitions on an ever increasing basis (Bloom, 2011). Employee turnover will continue to be a cause for concern due to the options available)

In the effort to remain ahead and to retain employees, organizations must never be static but must constantly review and renew their retention strategies (Budhwar, 2013).

Needs Assessment and Diagnosis

Research Design

This study will use the qualitative phenomenological study modified van Kaam method to capture perceptions of Human Resource professionals using semi-structured, recorded, and transcribed interviews. The use of in-depth interview sessions is appropriate for this study because the interviews aided in the understanding of lived experiences and identified recurring themes (Guest, 2011). The interview sessions will reveal a new phenomenon from the Human Resource professionals' lived experiences and perceptions. The systematic approach to organizing, analyzing, and synthesizing the data that will be provided by the modified van Kaam method will be an appropriate research design to accomplish the study's goals. Moreover, qualitative methodology is used for studying complex, real-world phenomena occurring in a natural setting (Price, 2011).

Qualitative methodology seeks a holistic or systems view of the subject under study, and the interaction is more personal as the qualitative researchers could conduct their research at the home or office of the participant (Tooksoon, 2011). This method provides valuable insight for the

researchers to apply when explaining unexpected outcomes in the research and identifies possible further avenues for research (Mello, 2014).

Data Collection

The research will prearrange the participants' interview date and time. Communication will be via email and will be followed-up phone calls to ensure effective communication and maximize scheduling coherence. The interviews will be conducted by telephone and will consist of semi-structured interviews with open-ended questions as the primary method of collecting data. The interview will follow the recommended steps to ensure methodical, quality interviews. Guest (2011) outlined steps for an effective interview.

These steps were to break the ice without rushing into the interview questions, to make the participants comfortable with the interview process, to express appreciation for their participation, and to offer the results of the research at the conclusion. Guest (2011) suggested staying focused by using a printed guide, knowing the questions, and asking them in a straightforward manner. Also important was ensuring a quiet location and, in a telephone interview, ensuring both the researcher and the participants will not be distracted by work or family. Finally, Guest suggested rephrasing the questions to receive sufficient and satisfactory answers, making the participants feel they are an important part of the research, and mastering the questions for a smoother process (Tooksoon, 2011).

Method of Analysis

Data collected will be analyzed immediately throughout the data collection process. Phenomenological studies tend toward this early data analysis (Tooksoon, 2011).enabling

identification of emerging patterns that can be clarified during the remaining data collection process. The researcher will exercise caution in this premature interpretation of the incomplete set of data to prevent skewing of subsequent data interpretation due to prompting of the participant by the interviewer. The research will follow the seven steps of the modified van Kaam method of analysis, which will include classifying the data elements by listing the expressions relevant to the study, reducing and eliminating the invariant constituents, and clustering and schematizing the invariant constituents (Budhwar, 2013).

Further steps will be identifying the invariant constituents as applied to the participant's complete record, constructing an individual textural description of the experience, constructing an individual structural description, and constructing a textural-structural description of the meanings and essences of the experiences (Mathis, 2011). From these individual descriptions, a composite description will be developed to represent the group in its entirety. Applying these steps to the research would entail capturing the data on a digital voice recorder during the interview, transcribing the raw data into a Word document, refining the content of the data, removing the personifications, and creating documents prepared for analysis (Guest, 2011).

The NVivo 7.0 software will identify the similar phrases and comments and group them into nodes. Once completed, the data will be verified by confirming each node listed the data relevant to the node; and the link will be followed back to the original document, where it could be further validated. The nodes outlined the emerging trends and themes (Bloom, 2011).

Proposed Organization Development Interventions

Time Schedule

All data will be gathered over the period of a few months to ensure systematic and methodical collection of data.

Resources Needed

The primary resources needed are the telephone, the recorder, and the NVivo software.

Budget

Estimated budget for this proposal will be around \$3000.

Needed assurances/clearances

The Informed Consent Form (Price, 2011).

Strategies and evaluation of the plan for Choiteram Supermarket

Human Resources were known for being employees' advocates and administrative in function, the transition has been to Human Resources' role in tactics and strategy .Human Resources have become increasingly involved in strategy. Organizations wanting to improve employees' workplace effectiveness cannot do so without involving both senior managers and Human Resource management specialists. Human Resources are actively involved in any organizational change (Bloom, 2011).Human Resources' positioning as a part of strategy as well as a part of administration, hiring, and firing, including disciplinary and grievance procedures (Wright, 2011).

Recruitment and Selection

Recruitment and selection are in many cases viewed as one single process but there is a difference. Recruitment is an overall procedure where hiring is done to fill the available or emergent positions while selection is a more detailed procedure that involves identification of the most qualified individual to fill a position that is vacant (Macdonald, 1995). In the process of achieving the aforementioned strategic plans, new positions will emerge that will force the HR department to conduct recruitments and other positions will fall vacant and this will call for a need to conduct selection (Tooksoon, 2011). During the expansion of the Choithram supermarkets, most of the middle level managers will be promoted to become senior managers in the new branches, which means that the new management positions will be filled only through internal promotions (Price, 2011).

This is going to work because the HR department has factored in the performance of these divisional managers and their competencies and a decision has been made that there is no need to source external managers because the management staff that is already there can handle the administration of the new chains with the required competencies. However, the HR will use external recruitment to source for human resources to run the new technologies that the company is going to install in order to cut the costs (Mathis, 2011).

This is because the technology cannot run itself and if the technology has not been in the company before, it means that there might be very few people in the current team that can handle the new technology. One of these cost cutting technologies is the use of the RFID that will help in inventories and surveillance (Budhwar, 2013).

The recruitment will follow the competencies model where the technological manpower will be recruited based on their past performances elsewhere in running the technology (Bloom,

2011). For the business partnership with the forever living international, the HR functions may be very tricky for the department because this is a new field that the company is venturing into and the current HR management may not be able to conduct selection and recruitment in a manner that is satisfactory. This means that the input of the HR department of the partners will be sourced because it has the expertise of selecting and recruiting the candidates in the herbal health and homecare field. In the selection and the recruitment process, the HR department will use the electronic method so that the company will have a wide reach of the desired candidates for recruitment (Guest, 2011).

Induction and Training

Induction is a very vital process in the modern business world. This is because it can enhance the well being and the productivity of the company. A bad induction can create confusion that will affect the productivity negatively because the staff will not be familiar with their functions or their place in the organization (Mello, 2014).

After selection and recruitment the HR Company will carry out an induction of the staff but the induction for the internally promoted and the externally recruited candidates will be done differently. For the externally recruited candidates, the induction will include the explanation of the culture of the company, company benefits, payment methods, hours of work, company hierarchy, , job description, the amenities in the company and even introduction to workmates. For the internally promoted ones, the main induction will be the explanation of the job description (Tooksoon, 2011).

Staff Training

Staff training will be conducted on the job and will mainly involve acquainting the new employees with the Choithram supermarkets' way of doing things. The employees were hired because they know how to do the job which means the training is not to show them how to do the job, but the company specific ways of doing it. Training will be a continuous process because all these details cannot be crammed within a day. Spreading the training over several days or weeks ensures that the employees are able to perform the duties assigned to them effectively (Mello, 2014).

Career Development

Career development for the employees by harnessing and developing their intellectual capacity and competencies is a factor that is critical to success implementation and it is something that in the past has been compromised by the defensive posture adopted by leadership.

The defense of the status quo should not be a case in an environment that is competitive. That is why the HR department will formulate plans where training is continuous to ensure that the employees do not remain stagnant in the face of a very dynamic world (Bloom, 2011).

This will include the motivation towards employees so that they can take career improvement course and ensuring that the company offers partial sponsorship for the individuals who are taking steps towards the advancement of the career. This is because the HR department understands that continued intellectual and competency enhancement is a vital asset to the company (Price, 2011). Apart from self sponsored career advancement courses, the company will still be getting career experts in various fields to conduct training on emerging trends in the

industry to ensure that the employees are up to date with the modern trends and goes on with his or her role as he or she trains (Tooksoon, 2011).

Conclusion

The aforementioned HR functions are strategic in nature and they will be performed in line with the three strategic plans of the company. Right from selection to compensation, the HR department will ensure that none of the functions delineates from the strategic visions of the company. This is because business excellence is not just about formulating visions and missions; it also entails the management of the process and the resources that will help in the attainment of the visions and missions (Budhwar, 2013). That is why all the above strategic plans must be aligned with the company's HR practices to produce an excellent business solution that will ensure that the turnover rate in the organization is reduced.

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